

THE DYNASTY OF AKILOV AND THEIR CONTRIBUTION TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEK DANCE

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Annotation: This article examines the role of national folk dances in the work of dancers and choreographers of our country, the specifics of the art of choreography, ancient values, priorities, as well as artistic principles, and the current objectives of the study. Isohor Akilov and his daughter Viloyat Akilova, who were able to show the traditions of Bukhara classical dance and its place in professional Uzbek dance, developed the traditions of Uzbek dance and studied the originality of the mastery of classical, folk and modern dances. it would be expedient to use it in the development of artistic processes.

Keywords: Art, dance, choreographer, ensemble, Bukhara dance school, mavrigi, method, rhythm, melody.

Today, about 100 dance groups operate in our country in order to develop the high spiritual qualities and values of the Uzbek people, to further develop and strengthen the Uzbek national dance art. Each of the dance teams has its own style and direction. These art groups work in the Tashkent-Fergana, Khorezm and Bukhara directions of the national dance school and contribute to the development of Uzbek dance.

Rock carvings and archeological finds in Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, testify to the antiquity of the art of dance. The antiquity of the Uzbek dance art, the richness of directions and schools stems from the fact that our ancestors were mainly associated with agriculture and handicrafts.

The art of national dance flourished during the reign of Amir Temur and the Temurids. The second half of the 15th century In the beginning of the 16th century, masters of dance nicknamed Sayyid Badr, Tahir Chakka, Mohchuchuk, Maqsudali, Katta Moh, Kichik Moh became famous. During this period, the art of dance developed in the field of folk dance and skilled dance.

After the emergence of the Bukhara, Khiva and Kokand khanates in the XVIII-XIX centuries, unique styles began to appear in the art of dance. In Bukhara, female artists were called musicians, in Khiva - khalfa, and in the Fergana Valley - yallachi. During this period, compact theatrical groups of women artists developed and their programs were performed at banquets and parties.

It is known that the Uzbek national dance art was further developed in our country in the 1920s. Dedicated artists such as Olim Olim Kamilov, Tamarakhonim, Mukarrama Turgunbaeva, Isokhor Akilov, Roziya Karimova created a national school of performance. Master artists enriched the art of national dance on the basis of centuries-old traditions and centuries-old values. This is especially evident in solo and group dances.

At the end of the XIX and the beginning of the XX centuries in the musical culture of Bukhara, along with the art of "Shashmaqom" and international dance, the musical dance "Mavrigiykhanlik" was developed. This type of art is unique to the Bukhara region. "Mavrigikhanlik" is a unique style of singing, similar to the musical culture of Iran and Azerbaijan. This style of singing was called "Movriy", and the performer was called "Movrikhon". The term "Movriy" was used by the Bukhara ayans at different times from different parts of Khorasan, mainly from the city of Marv (a city in the lower reaches of the Murgab River) to the Iranians who migrated to Bukhara.

Bukhara dances have been formed since ancient times and are distinguished by the courage and intensity of their movements, the richness of turns, semi-turns, horns and wheels.

The services of Sadulla Sadullaev (1883), Tojiddin Sobirov, Bibishirin Mamanova (1872), Chervonhonim, Tufahonim (1926), Oliyakhon Khasanova in the preservation of the traditions of Bukhara dance art in the transmission of the Bukhara dance school to the next generation Irrigated by their deep spirit of life, a number of dances played an important role in the spiritual development of our people and gained great educational value. Isokhor Akilov, who shaped the centuries-old rich heritage of Bukhara dance and its unique national features in his work, founded a professional Bukhara dance school in the art of national dance. Isokhor Akilov creatively used the past traditions of master choreographers and enriched it through his own experiences.

Isokhor Akilov began his career at the age of 14 learning the methods of the circle. This leads to the creation of a variety of dance techniques that are as necessary for the future dancer as air. I. Akilov gradually began to circle with his teachers at weddings in the mahallas. He manages to see the art of dancers from Bukhara to Samarkand, and then begins to master the wonderful but complex dance style of Bukhara. Learning these dances required a lot of hard work, practice and research from the young performer. Bukhara dances with such a variety of methods, melodies, hand and foot movements further enrich the

thinking of Isakhor Akilov, which plays an important role in the formation of a great artistic taste.

His coaches would also be pleased with Isokhor Akilov's diligence, hard work, thirst for new dance moves and boundless love. She is a master artist, famous performers of classical dance - G. Ulanova, RS Struchkova, M. Plisetskaya, Professor Lavrovsky, R. Zakharov, A.M. He was trained by choreographers like Meserer. The teachings of his teachers further enhanced his respect for the art of dance. I. Akilov

once again deeply felt the role of dance in life and that it is a powerful ideological tool to influence the masses.

I. Akilov, who loved the art of choreography, later began to stage his own dances, which he learned from his teachers AK Bek and Usta Olim Kamilov. He creates new solo and mass dance works based on Bukhara shashmaqomi melodies: "Kashkarchai Ajam", "Ufari navo", "Savti ajam", "Ufari ajam", "Soqiynoma", "Ufari Segoh", "Chapandoz". Isokhor Akilov made extensive use of national music and composers in the process of staging the dance. His dance "Shodlik" begins with the rock style of Bukhara shashmaqomi, and then moves from the ancient Uzbek folk songs to the song "Hay-yor-yor".

The dance "Shodlik", created in 1960, was staged on the basis of Bukhara Mavricha melodies - "Mahma Hasanjon", "Aspanjayiman". The artist made extensive use of examples of folklore, not only copying them, but also formed in his work aspects that meet the tastes of the modern audience.

Isokhor Akilov's choreographic activity was not limited to professional ensembles. In 1955, he and Margarita Akilova founded an 80-member song and dance ensemble at the Palace of Culture of the Tashkent Weaving Mill. Isokhor Akilov contributed to the professional development of the Bukhara dance school and introduced his wife Margarita Akilova and children - Viloyat, Zulaykho, Lola, Yusuf to the world of Uzbek dance.

I. Akilov's wife, a unique talent, People's Artist of Uzbekistan Akilova Margarita Bakhlulovna was born in 1920 in Samarkand in a family of artists.

Margarita has a passion for the art of dance since she was five years old. Margarita began her dancing career in 1932-1935. In 1935, Margarita married I. Akilov and devoted her life entirely to art and a life spent in collaboration with a similar fan of dance, dancer, choreographer Akilov. Margarita Akilova has been the leading dancer of the State Philharmonic of Uzbekistan for twenty years. Since 1956, the Tashkent Weavers' Combine has been the artistic director and choreographer of the dance ensemble of the Palace of Culture and has contributed to the development of the national dance art. Continuing the traditions of the Bukhara Dance School after Isokhor Akilov, Viloyat Akilova is one of the specialists working selflessly in the field. Over the years, he worked tirelessly to establish the Bukhara dance ensemble "Zarafshon". As a result of her research, Viloyat Akilova has staged more than 200 dance works typical of the Bukhara Dance School. The relevance of the study is determined by the study of the contribution of Viloyat Akilova to the Bukhara Dance School, who has been developing her innate talent for years as a professional dancer and choreographer, as well as artistic taste, demonstrating tireless work and creative potential. The reason is that Viloyat Akilova, who continues the traditions of the Bukhara dance school after Isokhor Akilov, is one of the specialists working selflessly in the field. As a result of many years of research, Viloyat Akilova created the Bukhara Doira Dars, which belongs to the Bukhara school.

Isokhor Akilov is the founder of the Bukhara Dance School, and Viloyat Akilova is the successor of the Bukhara Dance School after his father I. Akilov. In their performance, Bukhara dances acquire a special charm and legendary power.

It is their individual qualities that artists can feel this school of dance in their hearts, live in dances, feel the mentality of the region and reflect it in their actions. Today, Viloyat Akilova has staged many of the dances performed at the Republican Competition of National Dance Performers named after Mukaramma Turgunbaeva, and has been educating many students since then. Viloyat Akilova learned all the secrets of the Bukhara dance school from her father. The Bukhara tempo and rhythm can be felt even in the simple steps of a dancer. V. Akilova's appearance, facial expressions, and even her looks are in harmony with the Bukhara dance school. Isohor Akilov and his daughter Viloyat Akilova, who were able to show the traditions of Bukhara classical dance and its place in professional Uzbek dance, developed the traditions of Uzbek dance and studied

the originality of the mastery of classical, folk and modern dances. it would be expedient to use it in the development of artistic processes.

One of the urgent tasks of this research is to study in detail the role of national folk dances in the works of Uzbek dancers and choreographers, the originality of the art of choreography, ancient values, priorities, as well as artistic principles. An important task is to make a comparative analysis of the creative activities of today's worthy successors of the Bukhara dance school of our national dance art, the dances they create, to present them to the next generation in all their beauty.

The study of the current image of our national dance art shows that at a time when the attack of popular culture is affecting the education of young people, it is urgent to bring up worthy representatives who can explain the original national dance art to them. It is extremely important to preserve the chastity, charm, mystery, charm in the female characters depicted in the national dances created in the Eastern style. The art of dance is a powerful force that develops a person, introduces the people, the nation and the country to the world. So dancers are a delicate mediator on this path. A number of dances performed by Viloyat Akilova are becoming our golden heritage. The dancer is also doing a remarkable job in bringing national folk dances to the world stage and thus demonstrating the enormous potential of the Uzbek national dance art.

Today, Bukhara dance art is continued by Botir Rustamov, Salomat Rakhmonova and 3 dance ensembles in Bukhara region - "Bukhara", "Bukhara guzallari", "Bukhara mavjlari" and amateur folklore-ethnographic and dance groups operating in Bukhara region. are gaining ground.

The main activity of the song and dance ensemble "Bukhara" is the Uzbek national classical melodies - songs, traditional and wedding ceremonies and dances. From the day of formation of the ensemble to the present day, foreign tourists visiting our country, the city of Bukhara, watch the ensemble's repertoire with great enthusiasm and interest.

The song and dance ensemble "Bukhara guzallari" aims to develop and popularize traditional, solo and mass dances. This ensemble takes part in all national events, competitions, festivals and takes honorable places.

The Bukhara Mavjlari song and dance ensemble also operates in the traditional style and widely promotes the Bukhara dance school. In recent years, members of the ensemble have made a worthy contribution to the exemplary organization and conduct of such events as the Republic, participating in such prestigious state events as Navruz, Independence, international festivals "Sharq taronalari", "Ipak va zirovorlar".

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